

ACTIVITIES OF PUBLIC COUNCILS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: This article highlights the fact that the activity of public councils in Uzbekistan is one of the main mechanisms of public control and their activity, the role of public councils in increasing the social and political activity of citizens.

Keywords: Constitution, democracy, legal norm, law, civil society, public council, public control, Oliy Majlis.

Аннотатсия: Ушбу мақолада Ўзбекистонда жамоатчилик кенгашлари фаолияти жамоатчилик назоратининг асосий механизларидан эканлиги ва уларнинг фаолияти, фуқороланинг ижтимоий сиёсий фаолигини оширишда жамоатчилик кенгашларини ўрни ёритилган.

Калит сўзлар: Конституция, демократия, ҳуқуқий норма, қонун, фуқороллик жамияти, жамоатчилик кенгаши, жамоатчилик назорати, Олий Мажлис.

Аннотация: В данной статье освещается тот факт, что деятельность общественных советов в Узбекистане является одним из основных механизмов общественного контроля и их деятельность, роль общественных советов в повышении общественно-политической активности граждан.

Ключевые слова: Конституция, демократия, правовая норма, право, гражданское общество, общественный совет, общественный контроль, Олий Мажлис.

As we know, democracy is a form of government based on the recognition of the people as the source of power, their right to participate in the decision-making of state affairs, and the rights and freedoms of a wide range of citizens. The people regulate public relations thanks to a single tool called public opinion, public will, and the more powerful and influential this is, the more public relations become a compromising force. The administrative attitude to life, which is formed in the process of global information, makes it difficult to regulate, limit and eliminate various conflicts of interest on a daily basis. Public relations becomes a tool in the hands of politicians who use it to achieve political goals at some level. In this process, the mass media has a special place with its enormous, but still unknown, managerial abilities. An important problem of the

effectiveness of the public control system is related to the effective functioning of public councils and the importance of their decisions. Practice shows that the advisory nature of such decisions does not allow them to be implemented even if the authorities are obliged to justify the reason for refusing to implement them if they do not receive the approval of the executive authority. At the same time, not only experts, but also the officials themselves, who are interested in the more effective functioning of the agencies, emphasize that public councils should be transformed into a specific management body, and certain powers should be given to them.

The public council is an education with the participation of public members with an internal formalized structure, which is given certain powers by state bodies and consults with them on issues of adoption and implementation of state decisions. Community councils are one of the most participatory mechanisms. The main difference between community councils is the greater involvement of citizens in the work of governing bodies, which can be local, legislative or executive authorities. the public council is a permanent advisory body that conducts its work on a public basis, and the public council is established by the decision of the head of the state body. The public council carries out its activities on the basis of the regulations developed in accordance with the model charter and approved by the decision of the head of the state body, and the members of the public council, as a rule, are veterans who have rendered exemplary service in the state body, reputable citizens with extensive practical experience in the fields of public activity, as well as representatives of non-governmental non-profit organizations, mass media and other institutions of civil society are accepted.[1]

Community councils can be established for various purposes:

- consultation with experts on special issues; assistance in the development of legislation and the state budget;
- control over the implementation of government decisions;
- To perform some public tasks assigned by the state office.

The state's interest in taking public opinion into account. This interest can be expressed in public consultations on a wide range of issues, by providing citizens with all the information and educational activities necessary to understand public policy issues and make competent recommendations, as well as to obtain the opinion of various segments of the population. The main indicator of state interests is the use of recommendations received from public councils in their work. Duty of support by community councils. Community

councils involved in the development of legislation, government agency or budget work plan can often represent the interests of different community groups. This is done to help interest groups influence government agencies on issues of interest to them. Legislation plays an important role in supporting the activities of public councils.

Issues of public participation in the activities of state bodies at different levels. In its activities, the Public Council follows the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan, decisions of the chambers of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, decrees, decisions and orders of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, decisions and orders of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, this Regulation and other legal documents. . In various regions and regions of Uzbekistan, public councils were established in the presence of various state bodies and regional governments in order to ensure wide participation of organizations and citizens in the formation of state policy and its implementation.

Chambers of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Cabinet of Ministers, the Republican Council for the Coordination of the Activities of Citizens' Self-Governing Bodies, the "Nuroni" Foundation for the Support of the Social Activities of Uzbekistan's Veterans, other non-governmental non-profit organizations and every state body of the general public, including law enforcement agencies, The proposal to establish a public council under the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regional and Tashkent city governments was approved, and the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-3837 of July 4, 2018 "On measures to organize the activities of public councils under state bodies" was adopted.[2]

Legal acts in the field of protection of the rights and legal interests of citizens, legal entities, public interests and public opinion are taken into account in normative legal documents, decisions, as well as in state, branch and regional development programs, which are accepted as the main directions of the activity of public councils at state bodies. public control over the activities of the state body and its officials in order to ensure the fulfillment of the requirements, to perform tasks and functions entrusted to the state body and related to social and public interests, to provide state services, to implement transactions, contracts, projects and programs implemented within the framework of social partnership increase was determined.

Also, "public councils in the presence of state bodies perform the role of a "bridge" connecting the state body with citizens to ensure effective cooperation

with non-governmental non-profit organizations, mass media and other institutions of civil society;

generalization and assessment of social and socially significant projects received from non-governmental non-profit organizations and other institutions of civil society to state administration bodies;

systematic monitoring and comprehensive analysis of public opinion on the activities of the state body on the most important issues affecting the rights, freedoms and legal interests of citizens, conducting sociological surveys, including conducting them using information and communication technologies;

participation in the development and implementation of state programs and other programs in the field of fighting corruption in the activities of the state body, monitoring and analysis of the work carried out in the fight against corruption, as well as preparing proposals based on their results;

monitoring of the measures implemented to ensure the openness of the activities of the state body, analyzing the possibilities of obtaining detailed information about its activities, developing proposals for their further expansion; to study the conditions created for citizens' participation in the reform of the activities of the state body and develop proposals for their improvement;

participation in educational activities and educational events held among citizens on the activities of the state body, development of suggestions for improving their effectiveness;

comprehensive analysis of the housing, social-household, service conditions of employees of state bodies and their families, the conditions of providing them with qualified medical care, as well as the problems of social and professional adjustment of the dismissed or reserved employees, and improvement of these conditions based on the results of the analysis performs tasks such as making proposals in connection with it.[3]

Also, the activities of public councils are being organized under each state body. In particular, based on the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 1037 of December 26, 2019 "On measures to establish the Higher Education Council of the Republic" [4], the activity of the Public Council under the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan was established.

Information on the activities of public councils can be found on the official websites of the departments. In Article 5 of the Law "On Public Control" of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the activity of the public sector is based on the principle

that "subjects of public control should not be allowed to interfere in the activities of state bodies and their officials and exert illegal influence on them." However, in practice this principle is not fully implemented. On the one hand, the executive authority is interested in "adjusting" its operating system so that the department does not interfere with its work, on the other hand, the council has a certain right of independence as one of the main subjects of public control, but it is fundamentally suppressed. In addition, public councils have the right to establish commissions and working groups on issues within their competence, which may include representatives of civil servants, public associations and organizations.

Public oversight is a mechanism for the application and implementation of laws and decisions of public authorities in the person of individual citizens and through civil society institutions, as well as the evaluation of the results of these processes.[5]

What will the development of public councils lead to, will they become convenient and quiet advisors for the government or will they become a tool that affects the effectiveness of the activities of public bodies? The outcome of such questions depends not only on the leadership of the government or ministries and agencies, but also on the initiative of citizens, whose interests call for the protection of public councils.

Also, the Public Chamber develops indicators that assess the level of cooperation of civil society institutions with state bodies, their contribution to the socio-economic development of the country, the protection of the rights and legal interests of individuals and legal entities, establishes the cooperation of public organizations in achieving the UN Sustainable Development Goals, important normative- carries out public examination of draft legal documents. [6]

Modern political life in our country is manifested in the form of unstable, difficult to form and politically conflicting activities of many subjects with different sources, methods of action and ways to achieve political goals. Recently, when talking about practical politics, concepts such as propaganda, influencing public opinion, "public relations", etc.

Their composition will consist of representatives of various prestigious international organizations and many foreign countries.[7]

At the same time, the content of the concepts is not always clear and correctly interpreted, there is often confusion in the interpretation, which serves to apply these concepts despite the fact that many inconsistent definitions are close.

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